

Facies Association	Facies name and number	Facies description	Thickness	Depositional processes	Depositional environments	Spatial distribution
Facies Association 1 (Gravelly braided river)	Conglomerate with minor sandstone (1a)	Clast-supported, moderately sorted, subangular to sub-rounded, cobble conglomerates and sandstone lenses; shows clast imbrication, erosional bases.	~1-10 m thick	Bedload transport in a high energy stream flow.	Braided river environment (e.g., Kazanci 1990; Miall 1996; Collinson 1996; Miall 2010)	Northwest
	Matrix supported angular conglomerate (1b)	Matrix supported, angular to subangular, poorly sorted, pebble to cobble conglomerates in muddy matrix; lack of erosional base	35 cm-60 cm	Subaerial Debris flow	Subaerial alluvial fan and fan delta plain proximal to steep slopes (e.g., Maejima 1988; Tanaka and Maejima 1995)	
	Carbonaceous mudstones and sandstones (1c)	Carbonaceous silty mudstones and fine sandstones, rare pebbles, low bioturbation, pyrite and roots.	60 cm to 1 m	Suspension settling; river flooding from broken or overtopped banks.	Distal overbank to floodplain environment (e.g., Reading 1996)	
Facies Association 2 (Gravelly delta front)	Conglomerate with foresets and fitted clasts (2a)	Coarsening upward clast supported, pebble to cobble channel conglomerates; channel filled with cross-beds that shallow in dips upwards; shows fitted clast textures.	1 to 3 m thick	High bed load gravelly prograding mouthbars, channel incision with downstream accretion, jostling and abrasion between clasts.	Channel in a gravelly river system (e.g., Reading 1996; Bhattacharya 2010)	Northwest
	Bioturbated sandstone and mudstone (2b)	Carbonaceous, highly bioturbated fine to medium grained sandstones and mudstones with scattered plant material.	30 cm to 1 m	Mainly from suspension, burrows	Subaqueous, low energy interdistributary bay environment favored with burrowing organism (e.g., Jones and Schumm 1999).	
Facies Association 3 (Gravelly prodelta)	Conglomerate with deformed sandstone (3a)	Clast supported, pebble to cobble conglomerates with sandstone lenses, load casts, and abundant soft sediment deformation.	2 to 3 m	high-density gravel dominated river discharge, sediment gravity flows from slope failure, and fluidization.	Fan delta slope (e.g., Anadón et al., 2009; Renaut and Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010).	Northwest
	Matrix supported rounded conglomerate (3b)	Pebble to cobble sized, subrounded to well-rounded conglomerate clasts in carbonaceous muddy matrix.	10 cm to 25 cm	Subaqueous debris flows		
	Mudstone with normally graded sandstone and conglomerate (3c)	Siltstones interbedded with normally graded sandstone beds, conglomerate lenses, and dropstones.	Siltstone beds are up to 50 cm; sandstone beds are commonly 20-30 cm thick; conglomerate lenses are up to 40 cm.	High density turbidity current, vegetation rafting, and floating logs.	Lower fan delta slope (e.g., Boggs 2006; Renaut & Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010)	

Facies Association	Facies name	Facies description	Thickness	Depositional processes	Depositional environments	Spatial distribution
Facies Association 4 (Lacustrine)	Massive mudstone facies (4a)	Massive, highly carbonaceous mudstones with freshwater molluscs from <i>Hyridella</i> species (Gage 1952) and leaves of genus <i>Banksiaeformis</i> (Hill and Christophel 1988)	Mudstone beds are mm thick lamina collectively in thicker layers (mostly 10-12 m thick)	Suspension settling	Freshwater lake (Fossil Record Database; Gage 1952; Ward 1997; Cody 2015; Maitra 2020).	Centre, northeast and southeast, rarely in northwest
	Mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies (4b)	Carbonaceous mudstones interbedded with thin fine sandstone and siltstone beds with freshwater molluscs from <i>Hyridella</i> species (Gage 1952) and leaves of genus <i>Banksiaeformis</i> (Hill and Christophel 1988).	Mudstone beds are mm thick lamina collectively in thicker layers (mostly 6-8 m); Siltstone beds are less than 1 cm thick; sandstone beds are less than 3 cm thick.	Suspension settling with irregular and rare turbidity currents		
	Mudstones with normally graded sandstones (4c)	Carbonaceous mudstones regularly interbedded with sandstones, soft sediment deformation is common, bioturbation is rare.	Mudstone beds are 60 cm to 2 m thick; Sandstone beds are 5 cm to 20 cm thick.	Suspension setting with regular turbidity currents.	Lake more proximal to the shoreline; probably in the prodelta region (e.g., Renaut and Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010, Bhattacharya 2010; Topal and Ozkul 2014)	
Facies Association 5 (Sandy delta front)	Inversely graded sandstone (5a)	Coarsening and thickening upwards, fine to medium grained, inversely graded sandstone beds; no bioturbation; no roots.	30 cm to 1 m thick	High bed load sandy distributary channel.	Channel mouthbar in sandy river system delta (Ward 1997; Cody 2015; Maitra 2020).	Centre, northeast and southeast
	Bioturbated mudstone and siltstone (5b)	Moderate to highly bioturbated (BI:4), carbonaceous mudstone and siltstone with occasional beds of sandstone, sandstone beds show occasional ripple marks but lack fossils, normal grading and erosional bases.	Mudstone beds are mm thick lamina collectively in thicker layers (mostly 20 cm-1.5 m thick), siltstone beds are 20 cm to 1 m thick, and Sandstone beds are 2 cm – 20 cm thick.	Mainly from suspension with minor current flow, burrows	Subaqueous, low energy interdistributary bay environment favored by burrowing organisms (Boyd 2002; Maitra 2020).	

Facies Association	Facies name	Facies description	Thickness	Depositional processes	Depositional environments	Spatial distribution
Facies Association 6 (Sandy meandering river)	Crossbedded sandstone (5a)	Fine to medium grained sandstones, shows channel shape geometry, cross-bedding, basal scours and lag deposits.	10 cm to 2 m	Unidirectional stream flow	Meandering channels (Gage 1952; Nathan et al. 1986; Newman and Newman 1992; Boyd 2002; Ward 1997; Cody 2015; Davies 2019; Maitra 2020).	Centre, northeast and southeast
	Muddy sandstones with carbonaceous mudstones and coal facies (6a)	Muddy sandstones, silty carbonaceous mudstone to highly carbonaceous mudstone fining up to muddy coals at the top.	Sandstone beds are 20 cm to 70 cm thick; mudstone beds are 20 cm to 2 m; coal beds range from 40 cm to 1 m.	Channel shifting processes, such as meander cut-off and channel-belt avulsion; occasional periodic flood events from rivers; suspension settling.	Abandoned channels in floodplain (Gage 1952; Newman and Newman 1992; Boyd 2002; Ward 1997; Cody 2015; Davies 2019; Maitra 2020).	
	Inversely to normally graded sandstone (6b)	Inversely to normally graded sandstone, occasional interbeds of silty and carbonaceous mudstones, abundant plant material.	20 cm to 50 cm	Excess discharge during flooding that incises the adjacent levee and deposits as a crevasse splay.	Crevasse splays in floodplain (Gage 1952; Boyd 1995, 2002; Ward 1997; Cody 2015; Davies 2019; Maitra 2020).	
Facies Association 7 (Mire)	Coal (7a)	Comprises two subfacies; 1) black, hard, thick, and clean coals, and 2) alternating bands of clean coals and muddy/dirty coals.	50 cm to 11 m	Mainly from the preservation of organic matter due to low bacterial decomposition.	Mire environments away from an active river system; have poorly drainage systems, rich in vegetation, and low clastic input (e.g., McCabe 1984; Newman 1985; Moore 1987; Newman and Newman 1992; Sherwood et al., 1992; Boyd and Lewis 1995; Maitra 2020)	Centre, northeast and southeast
	Root-bearing carbonaceous mudstones (7b)	Low to high carbonaceous mudstones, interlaminated with variably carbonaceous siltstones and mudstones with abundant roots, twigs and other plant remains.	2 to 5 m	Settlement of suspended fine-grained clastic material and plant remains.	Low-lying marshy swamp in a lower delta plain or along a lake shore away from an active river system (e.g., Coleman et al. 1964; Bann et al. 2008).	